

EPR, Optical Absorption and Superposition Model Studies of Fe³⁺Doped Cesium Tetrabromozincate

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Abstract

An electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) study of Fe³⁺ doped cesium tetrabromozincate, Cs₂ZnBr₄ (CTBZ) single crystal is done at room temperature. The Fe³⁺ ion enters substitutionally in the host lattice replacing Cs⁺ ion. The local site symmetry of Fe³⁺ ion within the host lattice is orthorhombic. An optical absorption study is also performed at room temperature. Using optical absorption spectrum, the bands are assigned and Racah parameters (B and C) and cubic crystal field splitting parameter (Dq) are determined. Crystal field (CF) parameters and zero field splitting (ZFS) parameters are evaluated theoretically using superposition model (SPM) and microscopic spin Hamiltonian together with perturbation equations, respectively. The theoretically evaluated ZFS parameters are in good agreement with the experimentally observed values.

Keywords: Inorganic compounds; Crystal growth; Crystal fields; Electron paramagnetic resonance; Optical properties

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1. Introduction

Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) study provides information about local site symmetry (Mabbs et al., 1992; Weil and Bolton, 2007), defects responsible for the charge compensation in crystals, phase transition and distortion in lattice (Pilbrow, 1990). Optical absorption study is used to find energy level structure of impurity ion and crystal field strength (Wildner et al., 2004). Transition metal ion doped crystals are of more interest due to their applications in laser and optical fiber. Fe³⁺ ion in the iron group is interesting because of 3d shell being just half filled yielding the resultant angular momentum to become zero in the ground state ⁶S with spin S = 5/2.

The theoretical studies on the spin Hamiltonian parameters of d⁵ ion have been the subject of considerable interest. Various mechanisms have been suggested to contribute to ground state

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splitting of magnetic ion interacting with lattice. The mostly used perturbation procedure treats cubic field and diagonal parts of free ion Hamiltonian as unperturbed Hamiltonian, leaving the perturbation as the spin-orbit coupling, the low symmetry field, and off diagonal part of free ion Hamiltonian. This procedure was adopted by Macfarlane (1967, "a"; 1970, "b") for F state ions, which gives better results.

Cesium tetrabromozincate, Cs_2ZnBr_4 (CTBZ) shows structural phase transition between 130 K and melting point (Horiuchi, 2004). It can also show thermo sensitive photo-selective phenomenon like ammonium tetrabromozincate (El-Sayed, 1986). These studies developed our interest in CTBZ. In the present investigation, EPR and optical absorption study of Fe^{3+} ion doped CTBZ single crystal at room temperature (300K) are reported to obtain the information whether Fe^{3+} ion enters the host lattice substitutionally or interstitially and the associated distortion in the lattice (chemical and physical) produced due to impurity ion. The energy separation between different orbital levels and bonding of Fe^{3+} ion with the ligands are also determined. Crystal field (CF) parameters and zero field splitting (ZFS) parameters are evaluated theoretically using superposition model (SPM) and microscopic spin Hamiltonian theory, respectively. The theoretical ZFS parameters are in good agreement with the experimental values.

2. Crystal Structure

The crystal structure of CTBZ is orthorhombic with space group P_{nma} having the unit cell dimensions $a = 10.196 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 7.770 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 13.517 \text{ \AA}$. The number of molecules per unit cell is four i.e. $Z = 4$ (Morosin and Lingafelter, 1959). The ZnBr_4^{2-} tetrahedron appears to be significantly distorted by the steric pressure of one neighbouring Cs^+ ion.

3. Experimental

Fe^{3+} doped CTBZ single crystals were grown at room temperature by slow evaporation of aqueous solution containing stoichiometric amount of cesium bromide and zinc bromide with 0.1 mol% FeCl_3 . Transparent and light orange color crystals of Fe^{3+} doped CTBZ were obtained in about two weeks. The EPR spectra of single crystals were recorded at room temperature on X-band E-112 (9.1 GHz) spectrometer with 100 kHz field modulation. The single crystal mounted at the end of a quartz-rod using wax was aligned in TE_{102} cavity center to avoid RF field deterioration.

EPR spectra were recorded along the crystallographic axes **a**, **b** and **c** by rotating the crystal at every 10° using a goniometer. The optical absorption spectra of Fe^{3+} ion doped CTBZ single crystals were recorded on a Unicam- 5625 UV/Visible spectrophotometer in the wavelength range 195–1100 nm at room temperature.

4. Result and Discussion

EPR spectra of Fe^{3+} doped CTBZ single crystal at room temperature in ab plane for magnetic field B at 50° from **c** axis is shown in Fig. 1. When Fe^{3+} ($S = 5/2$) is doped in a crystal, it experiences a crystal field due to surrounding ligands. EPR spectra of Fe^{3+} doped CTBZ single crystal are found to

contain only five spectral lines due to fine structure transition of electronic spin $S = 5/2$ showing only one site of Fe^{3+} ion.

Fig. 1. EPR spectrum recorded in ab plane for magnetic field B at 50° from c axis.

When Fe^{3+} ion enters the host lattice of CTBZ single crystal, it can substitute or sit interstitially in the unit cell, which reduces the local site symmetry to orthorhombic as is observed in EPR spectra. The splitting in the energy levels of Fe^{3+} ion takes place due to the combined effect of crystal field and magnetic interactions (Rudowicz and Bramley, 1985; Gnutek et al., 2009). The experimental resonance fields are analyzed using the spin Hamiltonian (Abragam and Bleaney, 1970; Rudowicz, 1987, "a")

$$\mathcal{H} = \mu_B B \cdot g \cdot S + D \left\{ S_z^2 - \frac{1}{3} S(S+1) \right\} + E(S_x^2 - S_y^2) + \frac{a}{6} [S_x^4 + S_y^4 + S_z^4 - \frac{1}{5} S(S+1)(3S^2 + 3S + 1)] + \frac{F}{180} \{ 35S_z^4 - 30S(S+1)S_z^2 + 25S_z^2 - 6S(S+1) + 3S^2(S+1)^2 \} + \frac{K}{4} [(7S_z^2 - S(S+1) - 5)(S_+^2 + S_-^2) + (S_+^2 + S_-^2)(7S_z^2 - S(S+1) - 5)] \quad (1)$$

where g is the spectroscopic splitting factor; μ_B is the Bohr magneton, B is the external applied magnetic field. D (axial) and E (rhombic) are second-rank ZFS parameters, whereas a , F , and K are the fourth-rank cubic, axial and rhombic ones, respectively. The F and K ZFS terms are omitted because of the least effect (Radnell et al., 1975; Rudowicz and Sung, 2001). The above approximation slightly affects the fitted value of a (Rudowicz and Madhu, 1999). The direction of the maximum overall splitting of EPR spectra is taken as the z axis and that of the minimum as the x axis (Rudowicz and Bramley, 1985). The laboratory axes (x, y, z) are parallel to the crystallographic axes (CA). The local site symmetry axes, i.e. the symmetry adopted axes (SAA) are the nearly

orthogonal directions of metal-ligand bonds. The Z-axis of SAA in site I is coincident with the crystal **a**-axis and the other two axes (X, Y) lie in the bc plane.

The principal g-values for each site are obtained using the diagonalization procedure (Schonland, 1958). The process of obtaining principal values of the g-tensor is to rotate the magnetic field about three mutually perpendicular axes fixed in the crystal and to measure the g value variation in the plane perpendicular to each axis, respectively.

The field positions of transitions $M=5/2 \leftrightarrow 3/2$, $M=3/2 \leftrightarrow 1/2$, $M=1/2 \leftrightarrow -1/2$, $M=-1/2 \leftrightarrow -3/2$, and $M=-5/2 \leftrightarrow -3/2$ in terms of $\frac{D^2}{B_0}$ have been obtained as given in Eq. (3) of (Bleaney and Ingram,

1951). Since, the term $\frac{D^2}{B_0}$ in this equation disappears for $\theta = 0$ i.e. spectrum parallel to the axis

offers a direct determination of D and a. There are only five fine structure lines. The angular variation of fine structure in all three mutually perpendicular planes ab, bc and ca is shown in **Fig. 2**. The values of the spin Hamiltonian parameters g, D, E and a are shown in Table1. D and a should be of opposite sign.

Fig. 2. Angular variation of EPR lines for Fe³⁺ doped CTBZ in all three planes.

Table 1 Principal g values, their direction cosines and the parameters D, E and *a*.

Site	Principal g values	a	b	c	D	E	<i>a</i>
I	$g_x = 2.0708$	-0.0440	-0.9871	0.1539	61	8.6	8.5
	$g_y = 2.1434$	0.9984	-0.0488	-0.0271			
	$g_z = 2.1688$	0.0343	0.1525	0.9877			

D, E and *a* are in units of 10^{-4}cm^{-1} . The estimated errors for g, D, E and *a* are ± 0.0002 and $\pm 2 \times 10^{-4}\text{cm}^{-1}$, respectively.

The evaluated principal g values for Fe^{3+} CTBZ are in the order $g_x < g_y < g_z$, indicating orthorhombic symmetry of the magnetic ion in the host lattice (Bleaney and Ingram, 1951; Kripal and Singh, 2006). The average principal g value is 2.1275. The direction cosines of different bonds in CTBZ single crystal are calculated from X-ray data. The ionic distances and direction cosines of various bonds are given in Table 2.

Table 2 The ionic distances and direction cosines of different bonds of Fe^{3+} doped CTBZ single crystal.

Bonds	Ionic Distances R(Å)	Direction cosines with respect to crystallographic axes		
		a	b	c
Cs-Br(1)	6.4728	± 0.6422	± 0	± 0.7664
Cs-Br(2)	4.2392	± 0.4649	± 0	± 0.8853
Cs-Br(3)	3.7918	± 0.2208	± 0.2785	± 0.9346
Cs-Br(4)	3.7918	± 0.2208	± 0.2785	± 0.9346
Cs-Br(5)	3.7918	± 0.8397	± 0.5122	± 0.1800
Cs-Br(6)	4.2650	± 0.3222	± 0	± 0.9466

By comparing the direction cosines of the evaluated principal g values for Fe^{3+} doped CTBZ single crystal with the direction cosines of various bonds in the host lattice, it is found that the direction cosines of Cs-Br(3) bond are comparable with those for the experimental g_z . This indicates that Fe^{3+} substitutes at the Cs^+ in the crystal lattice. This is also supported by the ionic radii of Fe^{3+} ion (0.64 Å) being smaller than the ionic radii of Cs^+ ion (1.74 Å), which suggests the possibility of substitution of Fe^{3+} ion in place of the Cs^+ ion. Thus the Z-axis of SAA is along the Cs-Br (3) bond in the crystal and the other two axes (X, Y) are perpendicular to the Z-axis. The SAA system (X, Y, Z) of Fe^{3+} doped CTBZ single crystal is shown in Fig. 3. The charge-compensation model of Fe^{3+} site may be given as follows. The charge compensator along [111] requires that one of the Cs^+ or Zn^{2+} ions in this direction be changed. Further, for local distortion, only the nearest-neighbour (nn) Zn^{2+} and the nn and next-nearest-neighbour (nnn) Cs^+ are to be considered. The proper change in the local charge can be obtained most easily by removing one of the Cs^+ ions or replacing a Zn^{2+} by a Cs^+ ion. However, the latter change can be discarded because of the poor fit of a Cs^+ ion in a Zn^{2+} site. Therefore considering only Cs^+ vacancies, it is seen that the Coulomb energy is lowered more by a nn than by a nnn Cs^+ . Further, if nnn Cs^+ vacancies are there, one would expect nn Cs^+ vacancies also. It is, therefore, concluded that the Fe^{3+} site is due to a Fe^{3+} ion with a nn Cs^+ vacancy. The confirmation of this could be obtained by detecting interaction of Fe^{3+} with nn Cs^+ ions using ENDOR. The ENDOR study is in progress and the results will be published in recent future. The Cs^+ vacancy yields different relative displacements of the charge centers associated with Fe^{3+} and the

symmetry at the Fe^{3+} site is lowered to orthorhombic. The above model is similar to that of Fe^{3+} doped KZnF_3 crystal (Krebs and Jeck, 1972). It is seen that a is smaller than D , which is in agreement with earlier studies (Bleaney and Ingram, 1951).

Fig. 3. Crystal structure of CTBZ in which symmetry adopted axes (SAA) are shown.

5. Optical Absorption Analysis

The optical absorption spectrum of Fe^{3+} doped CTBZ in the wavelength range 195-1100 nm recorded at room temperature is shown in Fig 4(a)-(b). The spectrum consists of two bands in 195-325 nm wavelength range and 19 bands in 325-1100 nm wavelength range. The overall spectrum consists of 21 bands located at 1065 nm (9389 cm^{-1}), 880 nm (11363 cm^{-1}), 850 nm (11764 cm^{-1}), 830 nm (12048 cm^{-1}), 815 nm (12269 cm^{-1}), 795 nm (12578 cm^{-1}), 770 nm (12987 cm^{-1}), 755 nm (13245 cm^{-1}), 720 nm (13888 cm^{-1}), 695 nm (14388 cm^{-1}), 685 nm (14598 cm^{-1}), 645 nm (15503 cm^{-1}), 560 nm (17857 cm^{-1}), 540 nm (18518 cm^{-1}), 490 nm (20408 cm^{-1}), 470 nm (21276 cm^{-1}), 435 nm (22988 cm^{-1}), 415 nm (24096 cm^{-1}), 395 nm (25316 cm^{-1}), 295 nm (33898 cm^{-1}) and 250 nm (40000 cm^{-1}). Among the observed bands, the band at 20408 cm^{-1} is found to be sharp.

Fig. 4. Optical absorption spectrum of Fe³⁺ doped CTBZ recorded at room temperature in the wavelength range (a) 195-325 nm, (b) 325-1100 nm.

In a strong cubic crystalline field, the 3d⁵ electrons in Fe³⁺ are distributed in the t_{2g} and e_g orbital. Thus the ground state configuration is written as (t_{2g})³(e_g)². This configuration gives the electronic states ⁶A_{1g}, ⁴A_{1g}, ⁴E_g, ⁴T_{1g}, ⁴T_{2g}, ⁴A_{2g}, ⁴A_{2g}(F), ⁴T_{1g}(F) and a number of doublet states. According to Hund's rule, out of these electronic states ⁶A_{1g} lies lowest because the multiplicity of this state is highest (Low, 1957). The other excited electronic configurations are (t_{2g})⁴e_g, (t_{2g})²(e_g)³ and t_{2g}(e_g)⁴. These electronic configurations also give several doublet and quartet states (Figgis and Hitchman, 2000). As the transitions which contain the states having the same total spin quantum number are spin allowed (Harris and Bertolucci, 1978), all the absorption bands of high-spin Fe³⁺ result from spin forbidden transitions (Kripal and Mishra, 2005).

The bands at 9389, 11363, 11764, 12048, 12269 and 12578 cm⁻¹ are the split components of ⁶A_{1g}(S) → ⁴T_{1g}(G) transition (Dong et al., 2005). Bands at 12987, 13245, 13888, 14388, 14598 and 15503 cm⁻¹ may be the split components of ⁶A_{1g}(S) → ⁴T_{2g}(G) transition (Kripal and Misra, 2011). The bands at 17857, 18518, 20408 and 21276 are assigned as components of ⁶A_{1g}(S) → ⁴E_g(G) transition (Pandey and Kripal, 2011). The bands at 22988, 24096, 25316, 33898 and 40000 cm⁻¹ are due to the transitions ⁶A_{1g}(S) → ⁴A_{1g}(G), ⁶A_{1g}(S) → ⁴T_{2g}(D) (Kripal and Misra, 2011), ⁶A_{1g}(S) → ⁴E_g(D) (Kripal and Bajpai, 2010) and ⁶A_{1g}(S) → ⁴T_{1g}(F) (Figgis, 1976; Kripal and Bajpai, 2010), respectively. After assigning the energy states ⁴E_g(G) and ⁴E_g(D), the electrostatic parameters B and C are evaluated from Eq. (B.1) and Eq. (B.2) of Ref. (Pandey and Kripal, 2011). As the symmetry is lower than cubic, the energy levels are calculated using the Racah parameters (B = 943 cm⁻¹, C = 2034 cm⁻¹), cubic crystal field parameter Dq and Trees correction α. (= 90 cm⁻¹) (Mehra, 1968; Robert and weeks, 1974; Yu and Hou, 1987) with the help of CFA program discussed later. The calculated band positions are in good agreement with experimental band positions for Dq = 1030 cm⁻¹. The band positions and their assignments are given in Table 3. The value of Racah parameters for free Fe³⁺ ion is B = 1130 cm⁻¹ and C = 4111 cm⁻¹ (Yeom et al., 1996). The appreciable decrease in the values of Racah parameters from free ion values indicates a covalent bonding between the central metal ion and ligands.

6. Theoretical Investigation

The ZFS parameters of Fe³⁺ ion located at substitutional site are evaluated using the microscopic spin Hamiltonian (MSH) theory (Rudowicz, 1987, "a"; Rudowicz and Misra, 2001). Spin Hamiltonian of a d⁵ (⁶S state) ion can be written as sum of free ion (\mathcal{H}_o), spin-orbit coupling (\mathcal{H}_{so}), spin-spin coupling (\mathcal{H}_{ss}) and crystal-field (\mathcal{H}_{cf}) Hamiltonians

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_o + \mathcal{H}_{so} + \mathcal{H}_{ss} + \mathcal{H}_{cf}, \quad (2)$$

$$\mathcal{H}_{cf} = \sum B_{kq} C_q^{(k)} \quad (3)$$

where B_{kq} are the crystal-field (CF) parameters and C_q^(k) are the Wybourne spherical tensor operators. The crystal-field theory has been extensively applied to the study of spin Hamiltonian parameters of transition metal ions in crystals (Yeom et al., 1994; Yang et al., 2004, "a"; Yang et al., 2004, "b"; Gnutek et al., 2009). Point-charge model and superposition model (SPM) are generally used to calculate crystal-field parameters (CFPs) (Andrut et al., 2004; Rudowicz, 1987, "b"). In the

present study, we have calculated the CFPs, B_{kq} using SPM. The SPM is satisfactorily employed to several $3d^n$ ions (Rudowicz, 1987, “a”; Rudowicz, 1987, “b”).

Table 3 Observed and calculated energy bands and their assignments for Fe^{3+} doped CTBZ ($Dq = 1030cm^{-1}$, $B = 943cm^{-1}$ and $C = 2034cm^{-1}$) using CFA program.

Transition from ${}^6A_{1g}(S)$	Experimentally observed energy band (cm^{-1})	Theoretically calculated energy band from CFA (cm^{-1})
${}^4T_{1g}(G)$	9389, 11363, 11764 , 12048, 12269, 12578	11035, 11917, 12054, 12362, 12486, 12981
${}^4T_{2g}(G)$	12987, 13245, 13888, 14388, 14598, 15503	13673, 13719, 13847, 14166, 14330, 15066
${}^4E_g(G)$	17857, 18518, 20408, 21276	20561, 21039, 21349, 21415
${}^4A_{1g}(G)$	22988	22753, 22941
${}^4T_{2g}(D)$	24096	23659, 23890, 23901, 24056, 24178, 24780
${}^4E_g(D)$	25316	25067, 25206, 25552, 25663
${}^4T_{1g}(F)$	33898 , 40000	32229, 33373, 34882, 35353, 35547, 36338

In CTBZ the local symmetry around Fe^{3+} ions is orthorhombic. For the orthorhombic crystal field, $B_{kq} \neq 0$ only with $k = 2, 4, q = 0, 2, 4$. In orthorhombic symmetry, the zero field splitting parameters (ZFSPs) D and E are given by (Yu and Zhao, 1988)

$$D^{(4)}(SO) = \frac{3\xi^2}{70P^2D}(-B_{20}^2 - 21B_{20} + B_{22}^2) + \frac{\xi^2}{63P^2G}(-5B_{40}^2 - 4B_{42}^2 + 14B_{44}^2) \quad (4)$$

$$E^{(4)}(SO) = \frac{\sqrt{6}\xi^2}{70P^2D}(2B_{20} - 21\xi_d)B_{20} + \frac{\xi^2}{63P^2G}(3\sqrt{10}B_{40} + 2\sqrt{7}B_{44})B_{42} \quad (5)$$

where $P = 7B+7C$, $G = 10B+5C$, $D = 17B+5C$. B and C are Racah parameters describing electron-electron repulsion and ξ is the spin-orbit coupling parameter. In fact, the values of B and C for transition metal ion in a crystal are less than those of the free ion. The average covalency parameter N takes into account the covalency. Using the average covalency parameter N, we can write the Racah parameters (Jorgensen, 1971; Yu and Hou, 1987; Zhao et al., 1987) and spin-orbit coupling parameter as $B = N^4B_0$, $C = N^4C_0$, $\xi = N^2\xi_0$; where B_0 and C_0 are Racah parameters in free state and ξ_0 is free state spin-orbit coupling parameter. For free Fe^{3+} ion, $B_0 = 1130$, $C_0 = 4111 cm^{-1}$ and $\xi_0 = 589 cm^{-1}$ are used (Abragam and Bleaney, 1970).

Using the values of Racah parameters ($B = 943 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $C = 2034 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) evaluated from optical study of CTBZ, the average covalency parameter $N = 0.913$ is obtained using $N = (\sqrt{B/B_0} + \sqrt{C/C_0})/2$ (Wei, 2010; Pandey and Kripal, 2013).

The SPM gives the CFPs (Newman et al., 1978; Zhao et al., 1987) as

$$B_{kq} = \sum_j \overline{A}_k(R_j) K_{kq}(\theta_j, \phi_j) \quad (6)$$

where the co-ordination factor $K_{kq}(\theta_j, \phi_j)$ (Yu and Zhao, 1988) is an explicit function of the angular position of the ligand. The intrinsic parameter $\overline{A}_k(R_j)$ is given by

$$\overline{A}_k(R_j) = \overline{A}_k(R_0) \left(\frac{R_0}{R_j} \right)^{t_k} \quad (7)$$

where R_j is the distance between the d^n ion and the ligand, $\overline{A}_k(R_0)$ is the intrinsic parameter of the reference crystal, t_k is the power law exponent and R_0 is reference distance between metal and ligand. For Fe^{3+} , $t_2 = 3$ and $t_4 = 5$ are used (Yeom et al., 1996). As the co-ordination around Fe^{3+} ion is octahedral, \overline{A}_4 correlates Dq as (Newman and Ng, 2000)

$$\overline{A}_4(R_0) = \frac{3}{4} Dq \quad (8)$$

From optical study, we have $Dq = 1030 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Thus the relation gives the value of $\overline{A}_4(R_0) = 772.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. It is seen that for $3d^5$ ions, the ratio of $\overline{A}_2(R_0)$ and $\overline{A}_4(R_0)$ lies between 8 to 12 (Yeom et al., 1993). In our study, $\frac{\overline{A}_2}{\overline{A}_4} = 11$ is taken, which provides $\overline{A}_2 = 8497 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Table 4 Fractional position of Fe^{3+} ions together with spherical co-ordinates (R, θ, ϕ) of ligands in CTBZ single crystals.

Position of Fe^{3+} (Fractional)	Ligands	Spherical co-ordinates of ligands		
		$R(\text{\AA})$	θ	ϕ
Site : Substitutional (0, 0, 0)	Br-(1)	7.5180	40	0
	Br-(2)	3.6336	28	0
	Br-(3)	6.9747	52	21
	Br-(4)	6.9747	52	21
	Br-(5)	3.7918	79	-31
	Br-(6)	4.2650	18	0

Table 5 Calculated crystal field parameters and zero field splitting parameters together with reference distance for Fe³⁺ doped CTBZ single crystal.

	Crystal- field parameters (cm ⁻¹)					Zero-field splitting parameters (x10 ⁻⁴ cm ⁻¹)				
	R(Å)	B ₂₀	B ₂₂	B ₄₀	B ₄₂	B ₄₄	B ₂₂ /B ₂₀	D	E	E/D
Site										
$\frac{\overline{A_2}}{\overline{A_4}} = 11$	1.15	41385	16348	1493	1209	1186	0.395	66	7.6	0.115

In SPM, the non-zero CFPs, B_{kq} (Pandey and Kripal, 2011) of Fe³⁺ ion at the site is calculated by considering the parameters $\overline{A_2}$ and $\overline{A_4}$ as well as arrangement of Br⁻ ions around Fe³⁺ ion for the best fitted values of ZFSPs with experimental ones. Position of Fe³⁺ ion and spherical coordinates of ligands are shown in Table 4. For the reference distance of 1.15 Å, which is smaller than the sum of ionic radii of Br⁻ (1.95 Å) and Fe³⁺ (0.64 Å), the ZFSPs D and E are calculated using CFPs from SPM and Eqs. (4-5). The CFPs B_{kq} and ZFSPs D and E are given in Table 5.

The ratio $B_{22}/B_{20} = 0.395$ and $E/D = 0.115$ indicate that the parameters are standardized (Rudowicz and Bramley, 1985). The theoretical ZFSP values are in good agreement with the experimental ones. The CFPs B_{kq} obtained above are used to calculate optical absorption spectra with the help of CFA program (Yeung and Rudowicz, 1992, "a"; Yeung and Rudowicz, 1993, "b"). The energy levels of Fe³⁺ ion are obtained by diagonalizing the complete Hamiltonian within the 3d^N basis of states in the intermediate crystal field coupling scheme. The Hamiltonian contains the Coulomb interaction (in terms of B and C), Trees correction, the spin-orbit interaction, the crystal field Hamiltonian, the spin-spin interaction and the spin-other-orbit interaction. The calculated energy values are given in Table 3 together with the experimental ones for comparison as mentioned earlier. It is noted that there is good agreement between the two values.

7. Conclusion

EPR study of Fe³⁺ ion doped CTBZ crystal has been carried out at room temperature. The spin Hamiltonian parameters (g, D, E, and a) have been obtained. The results indicate that Fe³⁺ ions enter the lattice substitutionally replacing Cs⁺ ion. The optical study has been carried out at room temperature and the observed bands have been assigned to transitions from the ⁶A_{1g}(S) ground state to different excited states of Fe³⁺ ion. The Racah parameters (B, C) and cubic crystal field parameter (Dq) have also been determined. The appreciable decrease in the value of the parameters B and C from free Fe³⁺ ion indicates a covalent bonding between the central metal ion and ligands. The ZFS parameters for Fe³⁺ doped CTBZ obtained using CF parameters from SPM and MSH theory are similar to the experimental values.

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